

Small Bowel Obstruction Caused by a Food Foreign Body: A Case Report

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Abstract

Small bowel obstruction caused by alimentary foreign bodies is rare, particularly in patients without prior abdominal surgery. Delayed diagnosis may lead to serious complications, including bowel ischemia. We report the case of a 47-year-old woman with no surgical history who presented with acute small bowel obstruction. Imaging revealed mechanical obstruction with a feces sign and no signs of ischemia. Surgical exploration identified a mobile intraluminal food foreign body located 1.20 m from the duodenojejunal flexure. A gentle milking maneuver allowed transanal expulsion of the foreign body, which was identified as a fig, without the need for bowel resection. Postoperative recovery was uneventful. Alimentary foreign body-induced small bowel obstruction is uncommon but should be considered in patients without prior surgery. Computed tomography is essential for diagnosis. When feasible, transanal extraction following intraoperative mobilization represents a safe and minimally invasive alternative to enterotomy, with excellent outcomes.

More Information

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Introduction

Acute mechanical intestinal obstruction corresponds to a complete and persistent arrest of intestinal contents due to strangulation or obstruction [1,2]. It represents a digestive emergency that may be life-threatening. Its etiologies are multiple, including adhesions, hernias, tumors, volvulus, or foreign bodies [3,4].

The more or less complete association of four cardinal clinical signs—abdominal pain, vomiting, cessation of stool and gas passage, and abdominal distension—allows suspicion of the diagnosis and usually indicates radiological investigations. Small bowel obstruction of alimentary origin or caused by bezoars is exceptional, especially in patients with no previous surgical history, accounting for less than 4% of cases [5,6].

Management is medical and surgical and must not be delayed. Prognosis depends on the occurrence of intestinal necrosis and the effectiveness of treatment [7].

We report the case of a 47-year-old woman presenting with small bowel obstruction caused by an undigested food item. The main objective of this report is to contribute to knowledge regarding this rare and specific type of obstruction, particularly in patients without prior abdominal surgery.

Case Presentation

A 47-year-old woman, with no significant medical history and no prior abdominal surgery, presented to the emergency department with cessation of stool and gas passage associated with vomiting and diffuse abdominal pain, more pronounced in the hypogastric region. Symptoms had been evolving for three days, with no evidence of overt gastrointestinal bleeding.

On physical examination, the patient was conscious and hemodynamically and respiratory stable. The abdomen was slightly distended and tympanic, without guarding or rigidity. Digital rectal examination was unremarkable.

Plain abdominal radiography revealed central air–fluid levels suggestive of small bowel obstruction. Abdominal computed tomography showed distension of several small bowel loops with air–fluid levels measuring up to 34 mm in maximal diameter, a transitional zone located opposite the first two sacral vertebrae, and a feces sign upstream, consistent with mechanical small bowel obstruction without signs of ischemia. The colon was collapsed, and the terminal ileum was flattened.

Figure 1: Radiological Findings on Abdominal Imaging
A: Plain Abdominal Radiograph Showing Central Air–Fluid Levels Suggestive of Small Bowel Obstruction.
B: Abdominal Computed Tomography Demonstrating Dilated Small Bowel Loops with Air–Fluid Levels, an Identified Transition Zone, and an Upstream Feces Sign

Surgical management was undertaken via midline laparotomy. Exploration revealed a transition zone approximately 1.20 m from the duodenojejunal flexure, corresponding to a firm, mobile intraluminal foreign body.

A gentle milking maneuver allowed mobilization of the foreign body toward the colon, followed by transanal expulsion. The foreign body was identified as a fig. No bowel resection was required. Intestinal transit resumed on postoperative day 2, and the patient had an uneventful recovery, being discharged on postoperative day 3.

Figure 2: Intraoperative Findings

A: Intraluminal Small Bowel Foreign Body Identified during Surgical Exploration Prior to Extraction.

B: Extracted Foreign Body after Removal, Identified

Discussion

Small bowel obstruction caused by alimentary foreign bodies is rare in adults [8,9]. It is most often related to the ingestion of phytobezoars, conglomerates of indigestible vegetable fibers [10]. Dried fruits are frequently implicated, as illustrated in the present case [11].

Computed tomography is the imaging modality of choice, allowing precise localization of the obstruction, characterization of its nature, and evaluation of potential complications such as ischemia [12,13]. In our case, small bowel distension with a collapsed colon strongly suggested upstream mechanical obstruction. Surgical treatment is indicated in complete obstructive forms. When the foreign body is mobile, transanal expulsion following gentle intraoperative milking represents an effective alternative, avoiding enterotomy and its potential complications such as digestive fistula [14,15]. In the present case, this

approach allowed successful management without intestinal resection.

Prognosis is generally favorable when management is early and no ischemic suffering is present, particularly when bowel resection can be avoided [16,17].

Conclusion

Small bowel obstruction caused by a food foreign body is a rare but potentially serious cause of intestinal obstruction. The combination of imaging and prompt surgical exploration allows accurate diagnosis and effective treatment. Favorable outcomes can be achieved with early and appropriate management.

This case highlights the possibility of a less traumatic natural extraction of the foreign body when conditions allow.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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